

POLITICAL SCIENCES

POLITICAL AND LEGAL MEASURES FOR THE PROTECTION OF WOMEN AND MINORS IN GERMANY, RUSSIA, AND TURKEY. INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

Gafarova Alisa

Student,

Kazan Federal University

Abstract

The article examines the political and legal measures of women and minors protection and possible ways of international cooperation in facing such issues as violence and other forms of abuse and discrimination on the example of such countries as Germany, Russia and Turkey. It describes different approaches that exist in these countries. By describing implemented measures, the best practices and aspects for improvement can be detected. To achieve all the goals in a better way for women and children protection, the cooperation between governments should be provided. The importance of studying this topic is substantiated.

Keywords: women, children, violence, victims, human trafficking, prostitution, laws, government.

The issue of women and children protection is one of the most relevant to the present days. For instance, the annual UN's report on human trafficking from January 2023 informs about more than 450,000 victims and 300,000 offenders worldwide from 2003 to 2021. The report also indicates that girls and women accounted for the largest number of victims found in the world (61 percent in 2022). It highlights the urgent necessity for more serious and effective measures implementation to eradicate human trafficking, women and children abuse and violence. In order to do that, the efforts of states and international organizations must be united.

Studying German and Russian experience in this field is explained by the fact that Germany and Russia accept a lot of migrants annually. Moreover, Germany takes refugees. Turkey opens its doors for refugees and migrants too. Germany is a country of resettling of many migrants from East Europe and Asia. Russia in the 21st century has become the main choice of moving for migrants from Central Asia. According to the Turkish statistical institute: citizens of Russian Federation took the first place in the foreign immigrant population in 2022 with 25%. The German Federal Statistical Office- Destatis (Statistisches Bundesamt) presented the following data on the migration flows: 1,016,013 people came to Germany in 2023. According to the statistics, presented by the Russian Federal State Statistics Service in 2023, the number of migrants arriving in Russia from abroad amounted to 560,400 people, 491,000 of whom were from the CIS countries.

Germany, Russia and Turkey are active participants of international treaties of fighting human trafficking and violence against people. Germany, Russia and Turkey signed the «Palermo Protocol on Human Trafficking». International cooperation has a strong influence when it comes to the eradication of violence and human trafficking against women and minors. For instance, some crimes connected to human trafficking are related to crossing the border and offering services of prostitution or unpaid work abroad. This situation can be prevented or at least the scope can be lowered, if measures of controlling cross-border movement will

be stricter. Especially, when a large scale events occur, when the procedure of crossing the board is way simpler. Furthermore, it is also important to exchange experience among social system and security workers to improve their skills and to keep them up with up-to-date information, so they could learn from other countries approaches and methods. Raising the common awareness should also be tackled. It is crucial that women and children know their rights and a plan of actions in a critical situation. They, also, must be sure that they will be helped by the government and police officers. There should be no fear of declaring a crime.

Moreover, governments should work on different programs together. For example, there is a project that is funded by the European Union called «PIKTES (Promoting inclusive education for kids in the Turkish education system)». The main goal of the project is providing an opportunity of studying for refugees. For example, some refugees from Syria do not send their children to school as their sons have to work to provide for the family and girls are prepared for an early marriage. Social workers conduct different events to explain the importance of education and unacceptability of early marriages and their harm to the girl's health.

Signing international treaties should be combined with the strengthening of police work and creation of international platforms with the experiences of countries and methods of approaching the situations with abuse and human trafficking. Also, conferences on the above mentioned issues should be convened more often and be more effective in a way of exchanging the best practices of detecting criminals and providing help to victims. For example, victims of human trafficking and domestic violence can get help from local shelters and government in Germany, whereas in Russia victims can likely get help from non-governmental organisations. The system should be improved.

It would be worth mentioning that women and children are major victims of unwilling and slavery involvement into prostitution. In Russia it is prohibited to provide sexual services and to sell them. Although, the receiver is not punished, according to the law, but the one providing such a service can get a fine or prison

time. This lowers the probability of coming to police because a victim does not feel protected. In Germany it works the other way, prostitution is legalized and the workers get social insurance. In Turkey the services of officially registered prostitutes are legalized too, but such women are judged by society and considered to be «ashamed».

Prostitution contributes to the growth of demand on such services and victims of this activity. A government should take measures that would deal with the issue and would decrease the demand on prostitutes. Relevance of this approach can be proven by the «Swedish model». It is based on decreasing the demand on buying such services. Moreover, people, who were illegally or unwillingly involved into prostitution are not punished, additional work with them is conducted to contribute to the leaving of this business. However, this model is not perfect as receiving online services is not banned. According to the words of many victims, there is no difference between pornography and prostitution. Also, the Minneapolis Hearings, in HARM'S WAY, supra note 2, at 114 (testimony of T.S.) stated that the involvement in the sphere is not with the victim's consent. Laila Mickelwait has, also, conducted her research in the one of the most famous internet platforms of pornography content. She detected, that the majority of videos published there contained scenes of abuse towards women and children. Moreover, there were many scenes of crimes and tortures. Thanks to her, around 80 percent of harmful content was deleted. It is an example of a great progress in the sphere of women and children rights protection. If a victim knows that they can be helped, it is more likely that a victim asks for help.

I would also like to pay attention to the issue of domestic violence. There is still no law that would have protected women from domestic violence in Russia and there are women who are in jail for self-defense because when they have asked for help, police would not respond to their cries for help. One of the most striking cases of contacting the police and being refused to come is the tragic situation that occurred in November 2016. Police officer Natalia Bashkatova responded to the call of the woman who called the police for help.: «If you are killed, we will definitely come and describe a body». That day, Yana Savchuk, who called the police, was killed by her partner. The law of protection women and minors must definitely be implemented in Russia to give the police legal basis for intervention. Moreover, there is no restraint order, which puts women in great danger.

Women in Turkey are protected by the law against domestic violence, the law (№ 6284), and can go to police if they experience situations that violate their rights. But during more deep examination some difficulties connected to the implementation of the law can be found. For example, the law № 6284 of protection women against domestic violence exists, but it doesn't perform properly according to the words of organizations that protect women and lawyers. For example, according to the words of Ozlem Ozkan, an Istanbul lawyer: «When women who have been beaten go to the police, they are told: Don't file a complaint, it will only

make your husband angry». There must be a better monitoring system for the police and judges.

In Germany there are laws of protection victims of domestic violence. There are instructions that include hiding the information about the victim and giving a restraint order. There are also some complications when it comes to the work of social organisations because they have to deal with people who do not know their rights and be aware of traditions of certain cultures to be able to help them. A German woman is better acknowledged of her rights and less likely be involved into prostitution or other forms of exploitation, but a migrant woman can be scared of being deported to her home country with unstable situation. Another complication comes when social workers and police officers have to listen to the testimony of victims, who do not know German or other languages that are larger spoken in the world because a translator from their language into English can be related to the criminal. There are a many challenges that are met by German social workers. The approach to tackling the issue of women and minors protection can be improved, if the organs involved in the process of providing help will be united.

One of the solution of domestic violence and other kinds of violence is the ratification of the «The Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence» or «The Istanbul Convention». When a country becomes a member of the convention, it is binded with obligations that should be met by it. Moreover, there is a very effective mechanism that observes the measures taken by the country. In case of neglect on the convention, a group of experts called GREVIO can be meddled.

Adoption of laws should be conducted together with the measures of women's and minor's protection; it is crucial because this contributes to the eradication of large scale of cases of violent behavior. Strengthening measures to assist and protect victims of human trafficking, domestic violence and prostitution should be one of the priority areas of international cooperation. Only by working together at various levels, positive results can be achieved in the fight against this transnational phenomenon. The development of international norms, signing international agreements, the exchange of information and best practices, and joint activities of law enforcement agencies – all of this should ensure a comprehensive approach to addressing the issue.

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